

1st Annual Data Symposium

Monday, March 19, 2018 | Schedule of Activities

Time	Activity
8:15 am – 9:00 am	Coffee and check-in, Smathers Library Room 100
9:00 am – 9:10 am	Welcome remarks
9:10 am – 9:30 am	Keynote Dr. Forrest Masters , University of Florida, <i>Toward cyberphysical laboratories: a long-term view on data curation from a natural hazards researcher</i>
9:30 am – 10:30 am	Addressing Data Reproducibility Dr. Karl Benedict , University of New Mexico, <i>Opportunities for research data discovery and reuse – lessons learned from 20 years of geospatial data platform evolution</i> Viv Hutchison , USGS, <i>Towards Open, Public Access for Science Data: The Evolving USGS Experience</i>
10:30 am – 11:30 am	Enabling Data Discoverability Dr. David Chagaris , UF IFAS/NCBS, <i>Ecosystem-based Fisheries Management: Data Needs for the next generation of fisheries models</i> UF Advanced Computing and Information Systems Lab Matthew Collins , ECE, <i>Making Data in Archives Discoverable Through Standardization and Extraction</i>
11:30 am – 11:45 am	Break with LabArchives
11:45 am – 12:30 pm	Dan Majchrzak , Sunshine State Education Research Computing Alliance (SSERCA)
12:30 pm – 1:30 pm	Lunch
1:30 pm – 2:30 pm	Developing Current and Future Researchers Dr. Zachary Brym , UF/IFAS Tropical Research and Education Center (TREC), <i>Smart Farming: A Transdisciplinary Data Revolution for Agriculture</i> Bobbie Isaly , UF Data Science & Informatics (DSI), <i>Data Science and Informatics: Creating Student Led Data Science Curricula</i>
2:30 pm – 3:30 pm	UF Libraries as Resource Broker UF Data Management and Curation Working Group (DMCWG) – <i>Developing library/faculty research collaborations and partnerships</i> UF Academic Research Consulting & Services (ARCS) – <i>Providing library/faculty consultative support services</i>
3:30 pm – 3:45 pm	Break with LabArchives
3:45 pm – 4:45 pm	Networking session
4:45 pm – 5:00 pm	Closing Remarks
5:30 pm – 7:30 pm	Evening Reception hosted by Innovation Square, 647 SW 4th Ave (includes Innovation Hub tour)

Dr. Forrest Masters is a Professor in the Engineering School of Sustainable Infrastructure & Environment and serves as Associate Dean for Research and Facilities in the Herbert Wertheim College of Engineering. He earned his PhD in civil (structural) engineering from the University of Florida in 2004. Dr. Masters has received support from more than 40 grants from state, federal and private sources, including the NSF CAREER and MRI Programs. He also leads one of seven Natural Hazards Engineering Research Infrastructure (NHERI) experimental facilities for the NSF to study the damaging effects of extreme wind events on civil infrastructure. Dr. Masters has published more than 100 papers in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings and given more than 100 invited presentations. He serves on the Board of the Federal Alliance for Safe Homes, and recently served on the NIST National Advisory Committee on Windstorm Impact Reduction. In 2014, Dr. Masters was awarded the junior International Association of Wind Engineering award, which is the highest award in his field that recognizes significant and original contributions to research by an individual under the age of 40. He was also honored with the Outstanding Achievement Award in Mitigation at the National Hurricane Conference.

Dr. Karl Benedict is a recovering archaeologist and currently serves as the Director of Research Data Services in the libraries at the University of New Mexico. He brings over 30 years of experience in designing and using data management, discovery, preservation, and access systems to his role at UNM supporting researchers across the university in planning for and successfully executing their research data management strategies for maximum impact both during and following their research.

Viv Hutchison is the Branch Chief for the Science Data Management Branch in the Core Science Analytics, Synthesis and Library (CSASL) program in the US Geological Survey (USGS). Her team supports scientists in long-term management and release of science data through tools and best practices. She is currently Acting in the role of USGS Library Director. She holds an MLS from the University of Maryland College Park, and lives in Denver, Colorado.

Dr. David Chagaris is a research assistant professor at the University of Florida's Nature Coast Biological Station in Cedar Key. His research focuses on fisheries ecology and applied ecosystem modeling in the Gulf of Mexico and Southeast U. S.

Matthew Collins is the technical operations manager and scientific programmer for UF's Advanced Computing and Information Systems laboratory. He provides for the care and feeding of the technical resources, both human and machine, of the lab. He has 20 years of IT experience focused on open source software development in cooperation with scientists and engineers and recently (2016) was awarded a Master's in Industrial and Systems Engineering from UF.

1st Annual Data Symposium Speakers

Dan Majchrzak is the Assistant VP for Research Technologies at the University of South Florida. He is a founding member of the Sunshine State Education and Research Computing Alliance (SSERCA). His portfolio at USF includes High Performance Computing, the Advanced Visualization Center and Research and Education Facilitation Services.

Dr. Zachary Brym comes to us from the UF|IFAS Tropical Research and Education Center in Homestead, where he represents the Department of Agronomy. Zack's research and extension programs focus on agroecology from the perspective of crop physiology and plant community ecology. Zack helped develop the Data Carpentry for Biologists training materials, which are used by Dr. Ethan White in his semester-long course WIS 6934, and is working to make similar training available for agricultural scientists and farmers.

Bobbie, Anthony, and Tyler are seniors in Computer Science, Computer Engineering, and Industrial and Systems Engineering. They are all part of the executive board at DSI: Data Science and Informatics, holding positions of President, Vice President, and Lead Workshop Coordinator. Together, they function in this organization to bring data science resources and tools to students at the University of Florida.

1. **Toward cyberphysical laboratories: a long-term view on data curation from a natural hazards researcher** - Dr. Forrest Masters, University of Florida – Herbert Wertheim College of Engineering
2. **Opportunities for research data discovery and reuse - lessons learned from 20 years of geospatial data platform evolution** - Dr. Karl Benedict, University of New Mexico – Research Data Services (RDS)
3. **Towards Open, Public Access for Science Data: The Evolving USGS Experience** - Viv Hutchison, US Geological Survey (USGS) - Core Science Analytics, Synthesis and Library (CSASL)
4. **Ecosystem-based Fisheries Management: Data needs for the next generation of fisheries models** - David Chagaris, UF IFAS Nature Coast Biological Station
 - Fisheries resources are linked to one another through complex food web and habitat interactions, such that harvest of one species could have impacts on others. However, fish stocks are assessed and managed on a case-by-case basis with little to no consideration for effects on other species. Ecosystem-based fisheries management (EBFM) calls for a more holistic approach that accounts for environmental drivers, food web interactions, and habitat associations. A major impediment to EBFM has been the perceived lack of data to support ecosystem models. Recently, concerted efforts have been made to enhance data collection, archival, discoverability, and access. As a result, ecosystem model development has become more efficient and transparent. Additionally, critical knowledge gaps have been identified. While many challenges remain, overcoming the data deficiencies is the first step towards advancing EBFM and ultimately improve the management of complex fisheries ecosystems.
5. **Making Data in Archives Discoverable Through Standardization and Extraction** - Matthew Collins, Advanced Computing and Information Systems Lab, ECE
 - The Integrated Digitized Biocollections project (iDigBio) serves as the aggregator for digitized information from natural history museum collections from the United States and around the world. Data about specimens is an important part of systemics, ecology, phylogenetics, and many other disciplines; researchers in many domains need to be able to locate information that is relevant to them among the 108 million records in iDigBio. Data in iDigBio are mapped to a metadata standard called Simple Darwin Core so field definitions are agreed on. Even with standardized fields the actual representations of the data, both structural and logical, hinders the ability of researchers to find relevant information.

1st Annual Data Symposium Presentation Titles

In this talk, we will go through what we refer to as our data interpretation (as opposed to correction) process and how that makes data in large archives discoverable to wider audiences. We will also take a detailed look at how even unambiguous data like globally unique identifiers in archives need special treatment to make them useful for their intended purposes.

6. Sunshine State Education and Research Computing Alliance - Dan Majchrzak, University of South Florida – Information Technology

- SSERCA is a collaborative organization organized by the research computing departments at Florida universities. SSERCA, in conjunction with Florida Lambda Rail (FLR), seeks to provide inter-institutional support of computational and data intensive research and education. Because of the close working relationship among SSERCA members SSERCA has been successful in supporting collaborative projects across the state. SSERCA provides cyberinfrastructure at many of the state campuses, including high performance computing, data science support and advanced storage needs. SSERCA's true strength is in providing facilitation for research projects at various levels based on the technical needs of the project.

7. Smart Farming: A Transdisciplinary Data Revolution for Agriculture - Zachary Brym, UF|IFAS Tropical Research and Education Center, Agronomy Department

- Major advances in knowledge and technology have transformed farming throughout history; examples include the plow, selective breeding, chemical fertilization, mechanized cultivation, and genetically modified organisms. Systems that integrate these advances are often billed as revolutions for the benefits they deliver to farmers and the food system. Yet, advancements in agriculture are only beginning to respect the collective goals of production, environment, and society. Smart farms utilize information generated from the smallest scales of microbiota and plant nutrition to the largest scales of agricultural regions and food systems to improve agricultural sustainability. Smart farming programs, such as Best Management Practices and Integrated Pest Management, encourage monitoring and application cycles that maximize the effectiveness of management and resource conservation at farm scales. Farmers are challenged to develop simple monitoring programs and rarely make use of the information long-term or widespread. Similar shortcomings are common in agricultural research programs that evaluate a single management practice or technology through simple experiments. Smart farming, including transdisciplinary research and information technology, could be the next revolution in agriculture. The technology for smart farming is available and beginning to be adopted on farms, but the best management practices for data and information distribution lag

behind. So, how do we train farmers and scientists to adopt information technologies and best data management practices to farm smart?

8. Data Science and Informatics: Creating Student Led Data Science Curricula

- Bobbie Isaly, Tyler Richards, Anthony Codella, UF DSI

- In today's world, there is a pressing desire for data. People in all fields are looking to analyze available data in order to formulate best practices and techniques. At UF, researchers use data science for predictive models for political elections, bioinformatics, econometrics, machine learning, or roster building for athletes. However, there is no standardized curriculum for a solid data science foundation, and only a couple of classes on the subject are offered. DSI: Data Science and Informatics is a student organization at UF that strives to sit at the intersection of these groups, to provide that knowledge base and to promote collaboration between students and researchers in order to better the University as a whole. Practically, this translates into teaching interested students data science techniques, like web scraping and machine learning, in languages like R and Python. This talk will discuss methodologies to take students and research groups from little knowledge to the ability and educational independence to take on a project for themselves, and will help to answer the question, "How do we create and teach workshops in order to provide the tools necessary for students to grow from and apply to their own fields?"

CONTENTS

1. **Reproducibility Template** – (revised by former UF College of Business Student and UF Libraries OPS graduate student staff, Linfang Yuan) – (originally developed by DASLab, Harvard SEAS). <http://db-reproducibility.seas.harvard.edu/>
2. **Data Paper Template Version 1.0** – (developed by GreyNet International). <http://www.greynet.org/greyforumseries/datapapers.html>
3. **DCC Checklist for a Data Management Plan, v4.0** – (developed by Digital Curation Centre (DCC)). [http://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/resource/DMP/DMP Checklist 2013.pdf](http://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/resource/DMP/DMP%20Checklist%202013.pdf)
4. **UF Libraries Data Management and Curation Working Group (DMCWG) Charge (2016)** - <http://ufdc.ufl.edu/AA00014835/00076>
5. **Academic Research Consulting & Services (ARCS)** – <http://arcs.uflib.ufl.edu/>
6. **University of Florida Research Computing** – <https://www.rc.ufl.edu/>

Reproducibility Template Draft

Note: This draft is a revised version of SIGMOD Template 2016, most sections are the reorganized with some summarized information from the SIGMOD Guidelines: <http://db-reproducibility.seas.harvard.edu/>

The goal is to enable reproducibility of the raw data and relevant plots that the authors used to draw their conclusions. Authors should provide a complete set of scripts to **(1)** install the system, **(2)** produce the data, **(3)** run experiments, and **(4)** produce the resulting graphs along with a detailed Readme file that describes the process systematically for reproducibility by a reviewer or other researchers.

Commented [ly1]: This part is added and introduction is from SIGMOD Guideline

A) Hardware Specification

[Here you should include any details and comments about the used hardware in order to be able to accommodate the reproducibility effort. Any information about non-standard hardware should also be included. You should also include at least the following info:]

Commented [ly2]: This part is the original part C" hardware" in SIGMOD template . In draft, I moved it to the beginning because it's the prerequisite needing to be considered even before the software/environment setup.

- 1) Processor (architecture, type, and number of processors/sockets)
- 2) Caches (number of levels, and size of each level)
- 3) Memory (size and speed)
- 4) Secondary Storage (type: SSD/HDD/other, size, performance: random/sequential read or write)
- 5) Network (if applicable: type and bandwidth)

B) System and Environment Setup

[System setup is one of the most challenging aspects when repeating experiments. System setup will be easier to conduct if it is automatic rather than manual. You should test that the system they distribute can actually be installed in a new environment. The documentation should detail every step in system setup]

Commented [ly3]: This part is the original part A "Source code info" in SIGMOD template. A new name is given.

1) Operation System (e.g., the required compiler must be run with a specific version of the OS)

Commented [ly4]: Added based on SIGMOD guideline to give an idea why is part is very important and detailed steps

2) Configuration for the environment if needed (e.g., environment variables, paths)

Commented [ly5]: Added based on SIGMOD guideline— System part

Reproducibility Template Draft

- 3) Programming Language: [C/C++/java/...]
- 4) Additional Programming Language info: [optional, e.g., java version]
- 5) Packages/Libraries Needed: [an as thorough as possible list of software packages needed]
- 6) Compiler Info: [full details of compiler and version]
- 7) Procedures to test if the system is configured correctly
[Ideally, there is a script called: ./prepareSoftware.sh]

Commented [ly6]: Added based on SIGMOD guideline—System part

C) Datasets Info

- 1) Repository: [url]
- 2) Data generators: [url]

D) Experimentation and Measurements

- 1) Scripts and how-tos to generate all necessary data or locate datasets
[Ideally, there is a script called: ./prepareData.sh]
- 2) Scripts and how-tos for all experiments executed and measurements are taken
[Ideally, there is a script called: ./runExperiments.sh]
- 3) Scripts for a clean-up phase where the system is prepared to avoid interference with the next round of experiments.

Commented [ly7]: This part is added based on Guideline—Experiments part, The third phase

E) Data Representation and Visualization

[For each graph in the paper, you should describe how the graph is obtained from the experimental measurements.]

- 1) Tools that are used to generate the graphs (e.g., Gnuplot or Matplotlib)
- 2) Scripts (or spreadsheets) how to generate the graphs.

Commented [ly8]: This whole part is added based on the Guideline—Graphs and Plots part

DATA PAPER

This template provides you with a standardized, accepted format for drafting a data paper. Please consult the note box found under each field name for brief explanations and examples. The Data Paper consists of five main sections: **1** Overview, **2** Methods, **3** Dataset Description, **4** Potential Reuse, and **5** References.

Once you have completed drafting your data paper, please submit to journal@greynet.org. Upon receipt, the preprint will be deposited in the [DANS Data Archive](#) where the dataset is stored. Further notice of its publication in [The Grey Journal](#) will likewise be provided. The above email address can be used for all correspondence pertaining to your data paper.

1 Overview

Title:

NOTE The title of the data paper should focus on the **data**. Since your data is closely linked to a specific research paper, precede the title of your paper with **Data from “followed by the Title of your paper”**.

Repository Location:

NOTE A link to the repository home page and a DOI (or other persistent identifier) that links directly to the dataset.

Data Paper Authors/Contributors, Affiliations, and Roles:

NOTE

1. ▪ First name, Last name;
 - Author/Contributor unique ID (e.g. ORCID, ResearcherID)
 - Organizational Affiliation;
 - Author’s Role(s): Project Administration / Dataset Creator / Visualization / Draft Text / Review & Editing

2. ...

3. ...

Abstract:

NOTE A short (ca. 100 words) summary of the dataset being described: what the data covers, how it was collected, how it is stored, and a short description of its potential reuse.

Keywords:

NOTE A maximum of four keywords is allotted. Each keyword is separated by a semicolon followed by a space.

Subject Area:

NOTE Discipline or Community of Practice (e.g. Medicine, Engineering, Physics, etc.)

2 Methods

NOTE Describe the methods used to create the dataset (ca. 100-200 words), include the following sub-headings:

Steps – The series of procedures followed to produce the dataset. This should include any source data used, as well as software and instrumentation involved.

Sampling strategy – If relevant, outline the sampling strategy used to produce the data.

Quality Control – If applicable. Please list the methods used for quality control in the production of the data *i.e.* steps taken to normalize data.

3 Dataset Description

NOTE Enter your response after each sub-heading

File name:

The name of the file or file set in the repository/archive.

Format names and versions (if available):

Such as ASCII, CSV, Autocad, EPS, JPEG, Excel, SQL, etc.

Creation dates:

The start and end dates of when the data was created YYYY-MM-DD

Language(s):

Languages used in the dataset (*i.e.* variable names, etc.)

License

The open license under which the data has been deposited is Creative Commons, e.g. CC0.

Repository/Archive name:

The name of the repository/archive to which the data is uploaded: DANS EASY, Etc.

Publication date

The date the dataset was published in the repository/archive (YYYY-MM-DD)

4 Potential Reuse

NOTE Please describe the ways in which your data could be reused by other researchers both within and outside of your field. For example, this might include aggregation, further analysis, reference, validation, teaching or collaboration. This section should also include limitations to, or potential barriers for reuse. (maximum 800 words)

5 References

NOTE References cited here should be explicit to the Data Paper. When available, include a DOI, other persistent identifier, or link in each reference. See examples below:

1. Piwowar, H.A. 2011 Who Shares? Who Doesn't? Factors Associated with Openly Archiving Raw Research Data. *PLoS ONE* 6(7): e18657. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0018657>.

2. Giannini, S., [et al] CNR Pisa, Italy, 2016 Grey Literature citations in the age of Digital Repositories and Open Access. Seventeenth International Conference on Grey Literature. Conference Preprint available from:
<http://hdl.handle.net/10068/1024659>.
3. National Heart Lung and Blood Institute (US). What is a heart attack? [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): U S Department of Health and Human Services, National Institutes of Health; [cited 2009 Apr 3]. Available from:
<http://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/actintime/aha/what.htm>.

Upon completion of your Data Paper, please submit to journal@greynet.org.
The email can also be used for all other correspondence pertaining to your Data Paper.

Thank You!

Please cite as: DCC. (2013). *Checklist for a Data Management Plan*. v.4.0. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans>

DCC Checklist	DCC Guidance and questions to consider
Administrative Data	
ID	A pertinent ID as determined by the funder and/or institution.
Funder	State research funder if relevant
Grant Reference Number	Enter grant reference number if applicable [POST-AWARD DMPs ONLY]
Project Name	If applying for funding, state the name exactly as in the grant proposal.
Project Description	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the nature of your research project? - What research questions are you addressing? - For what purpose are the data being collected or created? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Briefly summarise the type of study (or studies) to help others understand the purposes for which the data are being collected or created.</p>
PI / Researcher	Name of Principal Investigator(s) or main researcher(s) on the project.
PI / Researcher ID	E.g ORCID http://orcid.org/
Project Data Contact	Name (if different to above), telephone and email contact details
Date of First Version	Date the first version of the DMP was completed
Date of Last Update	Date the DMP was last changed
Related Policies	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there any existing procedures that you will base your approach on? - Does your department/group have data management guidelines? - Does your institution have a data protection or security policy that you will follow? - Does your institution have a Research Data Management (RDM) policy? - Does your funder have a Research Data Management policy? - Are there any formal standards that you will adopt? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>List any other relevant funder, institutional, departmental or group policies on data management, data sharing and data security. Some of the information you give in the remainder of the DMP will be determined by the content of other policies. If so, point/link to them here.</p>
Data Collection	
What data will you collect or create?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What type, format and volume of data? - Do your chosen formats and software enable sharing and long-term access to the data? - Are there any existing data that you can reuse? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Give a brief description of the data, including any existing data or third-party sources that will be used, in each case noting its content, type and coverage. Outline and justify your choice of format and consider the implications of data format and data volumes in terms of storage, backup and access.</p>
How will the data be collected or created?	<p>Questions to Consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What standards or methodologies will you use? - How will you structure and name your folders and files? - How will you handle versioning? - What quality assurance processes will you adopt? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Outline how the data will be collected/created and which community data standards (if any) will be used. Consider how the data will be organised during the project, mentioning</p>

	for example naming conventions, version control and folder structures. Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented. This may include processes such as calibration, repeat samples or measurements, standardised data capture or recording, data entry validation, peer review of data or representation with controlled vocabularies.
Documentation and Metadata	
What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What information is needed for the data to be to be read and interpreted in the future? - How will you capture / create this documentation and metadata? - What metadata standards will you use and why? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Describe the types of documentation that will accompany the data to help secondary users to understand and reuse it. This should at least include basic details that will help people to find the data, including who created or contributed to the data, its title, date of creation and under what conditions it can be accessed.</p> <p>Documentation may also include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, vocabularies, units of measurement, any assumptions made, and the format and file type of the data. Consider how you will capture this information and where it will be recorded. Wherever possible you should identify and use existing community standards.</p>
Ethics and Legal Compliance	
How will you manage any ethical issues?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have you gained consent for data preservation and sharing? - How will you protect the identity of participants if required? e.g. via anonymisation - How will sensitive data be handled to ensure it is stored and transferred securely? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Ethical issues affect how you store data, who can see/use it and how long it is kept. Managing ethical concerns may include: anonymisation of data; referral to departmental or institutional ethics committees; and formal consent agreements. You should show that you are aware of any issues and have planned accordingly. If you are carrying out research involving human participants, you must also ensure that consent is requested to allow data to be shared and reused.</p>
How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who owns the data? - How will the data be licensed for reuse? - Are there any restrictions on the reuse of third-party data? - Will data sharing be postponed / restricted e.g. to publish or seek patents? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>State who will own the copyright and IPR of any data that you will collect or create, along with the licence(s) for its use and reuse. For multi-partner projects, IPR ownership may be worth covering in a consortium agreement. Consider any relevant funder, institutional, departmental or group policies on copyright or IPR. Also consider permissions to reuse third-party data and any restrictions needed on data sharing.</p>
Storage and Backup	
How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you have sufficient storage or will you need to include charges for additional services? - How will the data be backed up? - Who will be responsible for backup and recovery? - How will the data be recovered in the event of an incident? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>State how often the data will be backed up and to which locations. How many copies are being made? Storing data on laptops, computer hard drives or external storage devices alone is very risky. The use of robust, managed storage provided by university IT teams is preferable. Similarly, it is normally better to use automatic backup services provided by IT Services than rely on manual processes. If you choose to use a third-party service, you</p>

	should ensure that this does not conflict with any funder, institutional, departmental or group policies, for example in terms of the legal jurisdiction in which data are held or the protection of sensitive data.
How will you manage access and security?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the risks to data security and how will these be managed? - How will you control access to keep the data secure? - How will you ensure that collaborators can access your data securely? - If creating or collecting data in the field how will you ensure its safe transfer into your main secured systems? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>If your data is confidential (e.g. personal data not already in the public domain, confidential information or trade secrets), you should outline any appropriate security measures and note any formal standards that you will comply with e.g. ISO 27001.</p>
Selection and Preservation	
Which data should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What data must be retained/destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes? - How will you decide what other data to keep? - What are the foreseeable research uses for the data? - How long will the data be retained and preserved? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Consider how the data may be reused e.g. to validate your research findings, conduct new studies, or for teaching. Decide which data to keep and for how long. This could be based on any obligations to retain certain data, the potential reuse value, what is economically viable to keep, and any additional effort required to prepare the data for data sharing and preservation. Remember to consider any additional effort required to prepare the data for sharing and preservation, such as changing file formats.</p>
What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where e.g. in which repository or archive will the data be held? - What costs if any will your selected data repository or archive charge? - Have you costed in time and effort to prepare the data for sharing / preservation? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Consider how datasets that have long-term value will be preserved and curated beyond the lifetime of the grant. Also outline the plans for preparing and documenting data for sharing and archiving. If you do not propose to use an established repository, the data management plan should demonstrate that resources and systems will be in place to enable the data to be curated effectively beyond the lifetime of the grant.</p>
Data Sharing	
How will you share the data?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How will potential users find out about your data? - With whom will you share the data, and under what conditions? - Will you share data via a repository, handle requests directly or use another mechanism? - When will you make the data available? - Will you pursue getting a persistent identifier for your data? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Consider where, how, and to whom data with acknowledged long-term value should be made available. The methods used to share data will be dependent on a number of factors such as the type, size, complexity and sensitivity of data. If possible, mention earlier examples to show a track record of effective data sharing. Consider how people might acknowledge the reuse of your data.</p>
Are any restrictions on data sharing required?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What action will you take to overcome or minimise restrictions? - For how long do you need exclusive use of the data and why? - Will a data sharing agreement (or equivalent) be required? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Outline any expected difficulties in sharing data with acknowledged long-term value,</p>

	along with causes and possible measures to overcome these. Restrictions may be due to confidentiality, lack of consent agreements or IPR, for example. Consider whether a non-disclosure agreement would give sufficient protection for confidential data.
Responsibilities and Resources	
Who will be responsible for data management?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised? - Who will be responsible for each data management activity? - How will responsibilities be split across partner sites in collaborative research projects? - Will data ownership and responsibilities for RDM be part of any consortium agreement or contract agreed between partners? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Outline the roles and responsibilities for all activities e.g. data capture, metadata production, data quality, storage and backup, data archiving & data sharing. Consider who will be responsible for ensuring relevant policies will be respected. Individuals should be named where possible.</p>
What resources will you require to deliver your plan?	<p>Questions to consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is additional specialist expertise (or training for existing staff) required? - Do you require hardware or software which is additional or exceptional to existing institutional provision? - Will charges be applied by data repositories? <p>Guidance:</p> <p>Carefully consider any resources needed to deliver the plan, e.g. software, hardware, technical expertise, etc. Where dedicated resources are needed, these should be outlined and justified.</p>

Appointing Date: July 13, 2016

Today's Date: August 8, 2016

To: Plato Smith (Chair), David VanKleeck, Laurie Taylor, Hannah Norton, Erik Deumens, Valrie Minson, Haven Hawley, Matt Gitzendanner, Allison O'Dell, Christy Shorey, Fletcher Durant, Ed Neu, Peggy McBride, Joe Aufmuth, Sara Kiszka, Neelam Bharti, Laura Spears, Daniel Maxwell, and Todd Digby

From: Patrick Reakes, Associate Dean for Scholarly Resources & Services (*ex-officio*)

Subject: Data Management and Curation Working Group (DMCWG) Charge (formerly Data Management and Curation Task Force (DMCTF))

Thank you for agreeing to serve as a member of the Data Management and Curation Working Group. Attached is a copy of the committee charge which will be discussed at the first committee meeting. If you have any questions about the assignment, they can be clarified after discussion at the meeting. I am asking that the working group complete a status report annually by the end of December.

As you proceed in your work as outlined in the charge please keep in mind the importance of thinking about the issues in broad terms as they might affect other library units and the larger university community. Since data management activities are obviously very interdisciplinary and collaborative do not hesitate to involve other staff members in your work as it seems appropriate. This will ensure that recommendations are made with the benefit of information received from all affected areas.

Once again, thank you for agreeing to be a member of this working group.

All documents relating to this working group are accessible online from the institutional repository at UF (IR@UF) via <http://ufdc.ufl.edu/AA00014835/00076/allvolumes>.

Name: Data Management and Curation Working Group (DMCWG)

Members: Plato Smith (Chair), David VanKleeck, Laurie Taylor, Hannah Norton, Erik Deumens, Valrie Minson, Haven Hawley, Matt Gitzendanner, Allison O'Dell, Christy Shorey, Fletcher Durant, Ed Neu, Peggy McBride, Joe Aufmuth, Sara Kiszka, Neelam Bharti, Laura Spears, Daniel Maxwell, and Todd Digby

Description of Responsibilities: The DMCWG will develop collaborations, practices, and workflows that enable:

1. Developing and strengthening campus stakeholders communications and collaborations in positioning the UF Libraries as a partner in campus-wide data management initiatives and support
2. Aligning and integrating Office of Research, Division of Sponsored Programs, UF Research Computing, UF Informatics Institute, and UF funded projects' outreach and training developments/outcomes in the [UF Libraries Strategic Directions](#)
3. Developing a UF-specific DMPTool template for general Data Management Plan (DMP)reparation and dissemination
4. Developing and distributing a campus-wide research data management assessment survey, focus groups, and interviews as needed (See: [Data Asset Framework](#))
5. Developing and promoting Data Management Plan (DMP) & Data Lifecycle Management outcomes for all (1) internal/external Libraries' funded projects and (2) UF research community (See: [DMP Process Diagram](#) which integrates aspects of the [DCC Checklist for DMP](#), [USGS Science Data Lifecycle](#), and [UF Research Computing Infrastructure & Resources](#))
6. Assisting and developing funding opportunities for infrastructure & resources support for UFRC/UFIT/Libraries IT
7. Developing and implementing data management education, training, and workshops in collaboration/connection with Office of Research, Responsible Conduct for Research, UF Research Computing, UF Informatics Institute, and other campus training/workshops

Report Due Date: An annual report is due to Pat Reakes by the end of December annually.

Working Group Role: The Data Management and Curation Working Group (DMCWG) has an advisory role.

Recommended Decision Authority: The Data Management and Curation Working Group (DMCWG) is the recommended decision authority.

Anticipated Date of Decision Concerning the Working Group Recommendation: Any date of decision concerning the working group recommendation is determined by the DMCWG.

Minutes: A brief summary of the working group's minutes (actions items, decisions, assignments, etc.) is distributed to the DMCWG on the day of each meeting which is the 4th Monday in every month from 11am – 12pm in Marston Science Library, Room L136 or as otherwise noted.

Meeting Agenda: A preliminary agenda is distributed an hour to two hours prior on the day of the meeting.

Created: August 8, 2016

URL for this document: <http://ufdc.ufl.edu/AA00014835/00076>

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Research Computing hosts face-to-face trainings and outreach events throughout the year. Staff are available to present about computational services and consulting support at a departmental meeting or in a seminar series. On-demand training may be set up with Associate Scientist Matt Gitzendanner (pictured) for PIs and their staff to learn how to submit and maximize their HiPerGator jobs.

NAVIGATING UF'S RESEARCH COMPUTING ENVIRONMENT:

Each Wednesday from 10:00 a.m. – 5:00 p.m., Applications Specialist Ying Zhang (pictured) holds walk-in hours in the UF Informatics Institute. This is a great opportunity for faculty and their collaborators to learn how to efficiently utilize the services provided by Research Computing.

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